

ON THE INCORRECT USE OF THE WORD "PRINCIPLE" IN UZBEK LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *The author of this article has developed a comprehensive method for studying the semantic structure and functionality of lexical synonyms of the summarized mechanism based on simultaneous settings of Russian and Uzbek languages.*

Keywords: *complex research methodology, semantic structure and functional properties of lexical monuments, monetary resources and connotative meaning, trend in Uzbek is tamoyil, principle in Uzbek is tutum.*

The emergence of new components (subtleties of meaning, distinctive features, shades) in the lexical-semantic structure of a word is the contribution of masters of words, devoted lovers of their language, in particular, intellectuals, writers, journalists and, especially incomparable are the manifestations of fine taste, pure heart and ardent soul of people of the pen, as well as the importance of place. These people, possessing a real talent by nature, from within (intuitively) feel and understand the nature and features of their native language, strive to clearly express their existence through words, make a fruitful contribution to the process of forming new unique themes in the semantic structure of words in their creative work [1, 91-105].

Thus, each person in this area is important, first of all, because he serves to restore the rich cultural and spiritual heritage of our people, to find its worthy place, to ensure its recognition by society. However, in this regard, there is still much work to be done. In particular, in many cases there are many problems in spelling and orthography of words that came to our language through Russian language. Without denying the positive aspects of borrowed words, it should be noted that, according to the laws of language, a word that has passed from one language to another is considered borrowed only if it fully adapts to the rules of the acquired language, including the rules of spelling and pronunciation. However, according to the language policy of the former autocratic regime, words adopted into Uzbek language through Russian language were pronounced in accordance with the laws of Russian language and orthoepic norms, although in an unscientific way. Because at that time, according to the rule introduced by the ideology of the authoritarian Soviet regime to accelerate the policy of Russification, any words borrowed from Russian language, even if it contradicts science, had to be written as they are written in Russian and pronounced as they are pronounced in Russian, based on the rules of Russian spelling and orthography. For example, the word Russia is written in the form Rossiya and is pronounced as Rassiya, the term konferentsiya is written in the form konferentsiya and is pronounced as konferentsiya, Russian surnames such as Lomonosov, Mendeleev are written in Uzbek the same way as in Uzbek. Russians, and are pronounced as Lamanosov, Mindileev.

Nowadays, we have no non-scientific obligations. However, in the media space, including social networks, in a number of cases, they replace international words and terms borrowed from Russian language with Uzbek words, without sufficient study of the semantic structure of synonyms of these words, meaning and nuances of meaning, deliberately contradicting the principles and techniques of the rules of word usage. Although the meaning of one word does not

correspond to another, it can be noted that these words are used incorrectly in some cases. For example, the use of the word "principle" instead of the word "tamoyil" cannot be justified. Uzbek word "tamoyil" is not a principle. Tamoyil was assimilated from Arabic into Uzbek several centuries ago, and the meaning of the word "tendency" was assimilated from Russian into Uzbek in the last century.

Even under the former Soviet regime, for example, in Uzbek-Russian Dictionary (abbreviated: ORL), published in Moscow in 1959 (editor-in-chief professor A.K. Borovkov) and in Tashkent in 1988, the word principle was explained as follows:

"Know the PRINCIPLE. slope, inclination; correction, tendency." [7, 417]. It seems that the word principle in these dictionaries means precisely the tendency.

The word "Principle" as a book word in the "Annotated Dictionary of Uzbek Language", published in 2006-2008, sounds as follows: "PRINCIPLE 1 mile. Tendency, gradual direction (emphasis ours - B.D.) is explained and proven by examples: 1 The principle of bloodthirstiness is great among barbarian peoples. This is undoubtedly true! Oybek, Selected Works. 2..it is necessary to restore our ancient values and principles in our markets, to show the market as a mirror of our national values. From the newspaper" [8, 655]. In the five-volume dictionary of Uzbek language, the word "trend" is explained as follows:

"TENDENT 1" ***Direction of development***; interest, tendency, aspiration, direction. 2 The main content, idea of a certain thought, image or work. It is known that in the 60-70s, creative trends in the field of creating historical films received further development. S. Khodjayev, [8, 65].

From the analysis of the data presented in the dictionaries, it is known that the dictionary meaning of the word tamoyil is fundamentally different from the word principle. The word "principle" is based on elements that clearly mean inclination, aspiration, direction. Thus, principle is Uzbek meaning of flow, borrowed from Russian language.

"Persistent" attempts to replace the word "tamoyil" with "principle" lead to an inappropriately active use of a trend, clearly borrowed from Russian language, in Uzbek speech in an unnatural way, in particular, in online social networks.

For example, compare: "In ancient times, there lived people who had the profession of mirab. They were given a house at the end of the water. Because if the mirab does not distribute water correctly, the water will not reach itself. That is, even at that time, water conservation was strictly observed. But over time, this trend changed" (khabar.uz). In this text, the use of a trend borrowed from the Russian language instead of a principle undermined the coherence of the overall semantics of the text. Since the word "trend" was not used in Uzbek speech at the time when "people of the mirab profession" lived, then at that time Uzbeks used the word "principle" to denote the meaning of the word "trend". To prove our point, we will correct the error in this text by replacing the word "tendency" with the word "principle" using the method of replacement and comparison, and then compare and analyze the two texts. Compare:

Since ancient times, there were people who had the profession of a mirab. They were given a house at the end of the water. Because if the mirab does not distribute the water correctly, the water will not reach itself. That is, even at that time, water conservation was strictly observed. But over time, this principle has changed. Now the semantics of all the words in this text are harmoniously and logically connected with the general meaning of the text.

In some texts, it remains unclear in what sense this principle is used (principle or tendency?):

Some experts say that Lee Kuan Yew changed only his country, others say that he changed Asia, and others say that he changed the whole world... Therefore, the direction he created is considered a unique phenomenon and is called the "Miracle of Singapore" and had a unique impact on the development of mankind. In general, Lee Kuan Yew combined all this to reach the achievement of Singapore, based on these principles: to make it the safest place to live and work."

In this text taken from the newspaper, it is unclear whether the principle means a principle or a tendency.

Due to the fact that the principle cannot mean exactly the meaning of the principle, in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan and other current legal documents, the term principle is not used in the meaning of the *tamoyil*, the term principle is used in all cases. For example: "The system of state power of the Republic of Uzbekistan is based on the principle of separation of powers into legislative, executive and judicial (Article 11)." "Article 4. Basic principles in the field of education. The main principles in the field of education are the following: ..." (Law on Education).

A number of words formed on the basis of the word - *tamoyil* cannot be expressed by the word - principle. Including a fundamental conflict, a fundamental issue, a principled opponent, the leader's integrity and diligence; Just as a person without a principle who cannot stand firm in his opinion, so phrases, as well as sentences with their participation, cannot be expressed by the word principle. For example, compare:

"There are two contradictory principled approaches to the destructive war in the Gaza Strip; Today, Uzbekistan national team will play with its main rival - the Iranian national team (from social networks)".

It is considered that the meaning and nuances of such words as principle, unprincipled, cannot be expressed by the word *tamoyil* today.

It is not that Uzbek language does not have a unit that could express this concept, but there are a number of words that can be easily used in the principle sense in our language, for example, *tutum*, *tutruk* (*tuturuk*), *subut*, *burd*. Each of these words would more conveniently and fully express the meaning of the term *tamoyil* than the word principle, if these words were used in the media as a principle, and not as a principle.

The question is whether the word has its own meaningful proportion or not. In particular, instead of the word "principle" it is appropriate to use the word "tutum" of purely Uzbek origin: "principial" - "tutumu" strict (using old Uzbek word formation, you can also use the compound word "principle"). *tushtutum* "principle" - strictness, strict "tutum", "principled" - "tutumu", "unprincipled" - "untukut"). Compare: The situation was very tense// There was a fierce battle.

The word "principle" has not been fully adopted by Uzbek language, naturally, according to the rules of Uzbek language. Its "foreignness" is also hinted at by the letter (sound) "ts", which is not typical for Uzbek language, or rather, is completely alien to our language. The letter "ts" was introduced in 1940 of the last century in connection with the adoption of Russian-Cyrillic alphabet in Uzbek language as part of the Russification policy of the former Soviet regime. The way it is written (principle) and pronounced (principle) in Russian was adopted in Uzbek-Cyrillic alphabet and remains so in Uzbek-Cyrillic graphics, as well as in the speech of radio and television broadcasts.

It is considered that the word "tutum" can convey the meaning of the term "principle", but the term "principle" in many cases cannot express the meaning of this ability. For example,

compare the use of the word *tutum* in the following poetic verses (example 1), folk (example 2) and scientific methods (-example):

1) Your values are honor, education, nation, evidence// Don't let me see you, weak national worm - mangurts (Bakhtiyor Donirov. Intil wishes to the people).

2) Since time immemorial, it has been customary among our people that any competition is based on the principles of honesty. Wrestling, our national sport with a thousand-year history, is still a symbol of honesty (from the newspaper).

3) "Shaiboni Khan in many ways treated the regime of Amir Temur sincerely and respectfully, for example, he gathered scientists, poets and artists in the palace and encouraged creativity" [6: 17].

In none of these examples can the word *tutum* be replaced by the word *principle*, otherwise the text, written in harmony with the nature of the native language, would violate the semantic harmony.

It is alarming that in Uzbek language there still exist painful and negative situations regarding the correct spelling and correct pronunciation of words borrowed from Russian language. Such a situation is more common in words translated from Russian into Uzbek, where a phenomenon called reduction in linguistics (a change in sound in quantitative and qualitative terms as a result of weak pronunciation) is clearly present.

For example, such words as Moscow, lantern, democracy, constitution, October, November, mother, crow are written exactly like this, according to the rules of Russian spelling, the pronunciation is Moscow-Moscow, lantern-lamp, democracy-democracy, constitution-constitution, October-October, November-Noyabr, mother-mother, crow-varona. These differences in the spelling and pronunciation of words, characteristic of Russian language, are completely alien to the nature of Uzbek language. For example, many words in our literary language, such as *ota, ona, bola, opa, aka, olma, oy, kecha*, are pronounced as they are written. In our opinion, any word borrowed from a foreign language should be introduced into oral and written speech only on the basis of phonetics and grammar rules of Uzbek language. Then it will be in harmony with the ancient and rich spirituality of our people. Moreover, it does not harm the national identity. It is worth mentioning here that the English write "Moscow" and pronounce "Moscow" according to the rules of their language or express the word "Russia" in the style of Rashe.

Unfortunately, today even on television and radio there are many negative situations, such as the use of international words borrowed from Russian language in the speech of some of our journalists, contrary to the rules of Uzbek language. It is very sad that they, out of ignorance, understand this mistake as a sign of "civilization". It is worth noting that in some cases, instead of ordinary everyday words such as breakfast, lunch and dinner, adults and even our little children use words such as *zavtrk* (breakfast), *abit* (lunch), *uzhn* (*udzhin*) in their speech, while having a suitable alternative in our native language. It will not be a mistake to say that incorrectly formed concepts like the above are the reason that their use contrary to the rules of the language becomes a habit. However, as it is stated in the Annotated Dictionary of Uzbek Language: *KECHLIK* is a supper. When they entered the mosque after the evening prayer, *Aybodok* took out *kechlik* from inside. *Abdullah Kadiri, Past Days*" [8, 362].

A comprehensive methodology developed by us [3; 2; 1, 9-23] is using the methodological technique "Exchange and Compare", tries to use the Russian word "*udzhin*" instead of the purely

Uzbek word *kechlik* in the given example from the text of a famous work of art. Evening prayer, *Oybodok* took out *udzhin* from inside.

It is alarming that many of our compatriots inappropriately use Russian words in their everyday speech and even get so used to them that they do not even notice that they get into an absurd and funny situation in some cases.

In linguistics, as early as the 19th century, it was scientifically proven that language is a system. According to the law of systemicity, another system alien to it cannot function within any existing system. To put it simply and concisely, words borrowed into Uzbek language from other languages must adapt to the laws of our native language. For example, a number of words borrowed from Arabic and Persian, such as *bread*, *sky*, *school*, *pen*, *doctor*, *notebook*, *kitab*, in ancient times obeyed the rules of Uzbek spelling and pronunciation, entered our language and became an invaluable vocabulary.

In the 21st century, which is called the century of globalization, it is no secret that saving time is of great importance in the era of a fast pace of life. Reflections on the issue of an Uzbek alternative to international words borrowed from the Russian language will fill the imagination of everyone involved in social work. The fact that we face such a vital, but very delicate problem every day and cannot find a final solution to the problem and waste time is the reason that this problem remains relevant. (However, proposals for solving the problem have been regularly presented to the public since the first years of independence) [1; 2; 3; 4; 5; 6; etc.]

The author of this article has developed a comprehensive methodology for the comprehensive study of lexical synonyms, using the achievements made in the field of Russian (English through Russian) and Uzbek linguistics, in particular, in the field of lexicology, semasiology and stylistics.

Based on this original methodology, the connotative aspect of the semantics of nominative units in Turkology, including Uzbek linguistics, was comprehensively analyzed. Also, the lexical-semantic meaning of a word depends on the surrounding lexical environment and contextual semantics, based on scientific theory and practical evidence [2: 87-9].

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